

Development of membrane technology in BARC[†]

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BARC has been engaged in research and development work on pressure-driven membrane technology from laboratory to pilot plant scale and its commercial scale deployment, for sea and brackish water desalination into potable water, effluent water treatment and water reuse and in various industrial separations including decontamination of radioactive liquid effluents for their safe disposal into the environment.

This paper gives a brief description of pressure-driven membrane processes, reverse osmosis, nanofiltration, ultrafiltration and microfiltration. Selection of polymeric candidate materials, preparation of semi-permeable membranes and their characterization has been discussed. Various applications of these processes conducted on pilot plant scale have been presented. Large scale deployment of membrane processes for sea water desalination has been indicated. Research and development at BARC has thus resulted in the indigenous development of membrane processes for commercial scale operation.

Introduction

Industrial development in this century will be characterized by technologies that allow not only less consumption of available raw materials and energy but also permit recovery and reuse of all process streams with least damage to the environment. Membrane science and technology has a big role to play in this changing industrial environment. Unlike most of the other separation processes which are governed by 'approach to equilibrium', membrane separation is a 'rate governed process' based on preferential permeation of the desired species through semi-permeable membrane under (i) either the influence of applied external fields like pressure gradient or electrical potential gradient, (ii) or due to difference in chemical potential.

While most of the equilibrium processes call for two steps for the recovery of desired product (e.g. evaporation/condensation, sorption/desorption, extraction/stripping, loading/elution etc.) most of the membrane separation processes yield the preferred product in single step continuously under the influence of external field without involving any phase change. Generally carried out at ambient temperature, the membrane processes call for less energy as well as chemical inputs compared to other conventional separation processes. Accordingly, membrane technology is branded as environmentally benign and clean technology.

The real breakthrough in membranes came in 1970 with the development of reverse osmosis (RO) process for desalination of saline waters. In recent years, membrane

separation process¹ has found large scale applications in several areas starting from desalination, water and waste water treatment, removal of organics from aqueous and non-aqueous systems, chemical vapour recovery, separation of azeotropic liquid mixtures and selective separation of metal ions including rare earths and actinides from process streams. A number of newer developments in membrane processes have taken place² which include development of novel inorganic membranes, such as ionic membrane/bipolar membrane systems for electrolytic cell applications and proton conduction ion-exchange membranes for low temperature fuel cell application.

BARC has been engaged in membrane research for more than two decades and some of the major development activities particularly dealing with pressure-driven membrane processes, are reviewed in this paper. First a brief description of these processes are given followed by synthesis of polymers, preparation of membranes and their characterization and finally their numerous applications are presented.

Pressure driven membrane processes

Pressure-driven membrane processes, viz. reverse osmosis (RO), nanofiltration (NF), ultrafiltration (UF) and microfiltration (MF) are the most developed commercial membrane processes³. They utilize semi-permeable polymeric membranes to separate the dissolved solutes present in aqueous solutions and the characteristics of

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

various pressure-driven membrane processes are given in Table 1. Depending on the nature of the solute species, different membrane processes are adopted for the preferential separation tasks. It may be observed that the basic process involved in purification of water by MF and UF membranes is purely pore size dependent (physical in nature) while that for NF is primarily physical with some chemical interaction involved (that allows monovalent ions to pass through but restricts multivalent ions) depending on the nature of surface charge on membrane and that of the permeating ionic charge. RO involves mostly physicochemical interaction. RO membranes have a balanced hydrophilic/hydrophobic character and they separate dissolved inorganic as well as organic solutes.

Table 1. Characteristics of pressure-driven membrane processes*

Parameter	RO	NF	UF	MF
Pore size (Å)	5–10	10–20	20–100	0.02–1 (μ)
Solute size (MW)	<300	<750	>750	>100000
Pressure (bar)	20–60	10–15	2–5	1–2
Application	Desalination, water and effluent water treatment, concentration of process streams	Removal of colour, organics, hardness, separation of organics from inorganics, softening	Food processing, pharmaceutical, dairy, oil removal, drinking water supply	Disinfection, colloidal and suspension removal

*RO = Reverse osmosis, NF = nanofiltration, UF = ultrafiltration, MF = microfiltration.

Reverse osmosis :

Reverse osmosis is the first membrane process adopted for the purpose of desalination and water treatment. It is also extensively used for waste water treatment for recovery of water for reuse and in many process industries. There have been significant developments in recent years concerning energy recovery from reject water stream as well as in operational aspects of RO process like operation at elevated temperature and use of combo membrane process for increased product recovery etc. resulting in significant cost reduction.

Today there are large number of RO plants worldwide providing fresh water from desalination of sea and brackish water sources. Most of the desalination plants are located in Gulf countries due to their acute water problem and availability of cheap energy sources. However, to cope with the demand of industrial and domestic uses of water in water scarce area, many industries in India are setting up RO desalination plants to meet their needs of power and water in

such areas.

Nanofiltration process :

Nanofiltration (NF) is often considered as water softening and partial desalination technique. Nanofiltration membranes which have the ability to selectively retain bivalent solutes may lead to lower hardness and sulfates as well as salinities of the treated seawater feed which in turn has the potential to yield high recoveries in RO plants. Nanofiltration has been successfully adopted for separation of dyes from salt mixtures, separation of enzymes, and removal of halomethanes from drinking water. Recently these membrane systems have been shown to be capable of removing nitrates, fluorides and arsenic from drinking water sources.

Ultrafiltration process :

The UF process has found immense use in food processing, agro-products and other biotechnological applications. This process employs a porous membrane barrier characterized by specified molecular weight cut off (MWCO) operating at low pressures. The usefulness of UF process in water treatment lies in colloidal filtration and turbidity removal. In recent years large capacity UF plants based on cellulose acetate and polysulfone capillary membranes (which are preferred due to their excellent resistance to acids, alkalies, and oxidizing environments) have been deployed for drinking water supply from river waters in Europe.

Recently, UF membranes are being considered for pre-treatment in seawater RO plants in place of conventional methods. The UF membrane systems eliminate the requirement of clariflocculators, pressure sand filters, activated carbon filter and cartridge filter. The need for chlorination is also obviated as the UF membranes remove all the microorganisms, which tend to foul the RO membrane. With low turbidity of raw water, the membrane-life of UF treated water is reported to increase to at least 5 years.

Microfiltration :

The microfiltration membranes which were essentially developed for pharmaceutical and microbiological applications are suggested to be useful for various water treatment applications. The conventional sterilization/disinfection units for drinking water are based on micron size ceramic filter, carbon filter, iodized resin and UV sterilizer. All these systems have limitations of some kind or other. The microfiltration membrane (polysulfone and fluoro polymers) filters of submicron size do not require use of chemicals or electric power and can remove the microorganisms from drinking water at the prevailing tap water pressures. This process has tremendous potential in treatment of surface

waters as well as moderate effluent streams.

Membrane materials, synthesis and characterization

Polymeric membrane development :

The selection of polymer candidates for a specific separation involves several requirements of physicochemical properties, like high molecular weight, polar/nonpolar character, optimum solubility parameter, macromolecular architecture and structure etc.⁴⁻⁶. Polymers which are generally used for membrane applications could be classified as cellulosic and non-cellulosic polymers.

Cellulose or regenerated cellulose is the most important naturally occurring polymer for membrane applications, particularly dialysis. The high structural regularity and intermolecular hydrogen bonding of its hydroxyl groups make cellulose difficult to dissolve. Principal solvent for the manufacture of cellulose membranes is an aqueous solution of cuprammonium hydroxide.

Cellulose can be modified by reaction between suitable monomers and the active hydrogens of the hydroxyl groups, to form cellulose derivatives. The most important derivatives of cellulose for membrane applications are inorganic (nitrate) and organic (acetate) esters. Cellulose nitrate (CN) was the first polymer utilized to produce filtration membranes. Cellulose acetate (CA), being less inflammable and cheaper, has overtaken cellulose nitrate. Today cellulose acetate is considered a versatile⁷ membrane polymer due to its low cost, outstanding tractability and reasonable resistance to chlorine attack. Cellulose acetate was utilized by Loeb and Sourirajan in their classic development of integrally skinned membranes which heralded the modern membrane era⁸.

Cellulose triacetate (CTA) is a polymer of importance for microfiltration, and reverse osmosis membranes. In reverse osmosis for single stage sea water desalination it is used in hollow fibre form. The utility of CTA is due to its increasing permselectivity with increasing degree of acetylation. CA/CTA blend polymer, with its high acetyl content and residual hydroxy group, provides high water permeability and permselectivity adequate for brackish water desalination. Limitations of cellulose derivatives are borderline glass transition temperature (68.6°) which limits its utility at elevated temperatures and pressure, a tendency to undergo hydrolysis in alkaline media and a lack of resistance to attack by microorganisms. BARC has developed the laboratory knowhow for preparation of flat sheet reverse osmosis membranes from CA, and CA/CTA blend membrane systems for desalination of brackish and high saline brackish waters.

Fully aromatic polyamides (PA) are suitable as mem-

brane polymers with exceptional chemical, thermal, and hydrolytic stability and permselectivity⁹. Polyamides are polycondensation reaction products of diamines and diacids or diacid chlorides. The most important structural feature of polyamides is the CONH group, the amide link which has a strong capacity for hydrogen bonding. Optimum balance between processing and end-use properties was achieved by randomizing the molecular structure through the use of *meta*- and *para*-substituted monomers. Some recent aromatic polyamides for desalination are prepared from all *meta*-substituted monomers, approximately 10% of whose aromatic rings are sulfonated. These aromatic polyamides however lack chlorine resistance due to electrophilic substitution of aromatic rings by chlorine which disrupts intermolecular hydrogen bonding resulting in increased permeability and reduced permselectivity. A number of aromatic polyamides, namely, polyamide hydrazide, polyetheramide hydrazide, polysulfonamide hydrazide and polysulfonamide have been synthesized in BARC for membrane applications¹⁰⁻¹³. The chemical structures of different types of polyamide polymer-membrane developed in BARC are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Chemical structures of different types of polyamide membranes

Polyamide	Structure (Repeat unit)
Polyamide	
Polyamide hydrazide	
Polyetheramide-hydrazide	
Polysulfonamide	
Polybenzimidazole	
Polysulfone	
Polyether sulfone	

The high-melting temperatures of aromatic polyamides and related polymers require their synthesis by interfacial or low temperature polycondensation techniques. Interfacial polycondensation is a versatile technique wherein neither high purity of intermediates nor exact stoichiometry need be maintained and can be adopted for the direct synthesis of thin film composite (TFC) membrane *in situ* over macroporous substrates.

Polysulfone (PS) is the polymeric product of the reaction between the disodium salt of bisphenol-A and dichlorodiphenyl sulfone. Among the properties which qualify PS as an outstanding membrane polymer is its high thermal

and oxidative stability, high strength and resistance to extremes of pH. The closely related polyethersulfone (PES) is totally devoid of aliphatic hydrocarbon groups and exhibits even higher thermal stability. The sulfone groups adjacent to the aromatic ring act as a sink for the electrons and confers thermal and oxidative stability. Because of the aromatic moieties, membranes from both these polymers are resistant to high energy irradiation.

Synthesis and characterization of ultrafiltration membrane systems from CA and polysulfones are extensively studied in BARC and reported^{14,15}. Another desirable property of the aromatic groups is that they may be substituted thereby providing an excellent means of introduction of ion exchange groups and potential crosslinking sites. Nitrated polysulfones are found¹⁶ to be promising candidates for preparing nanofiltration membranes. Membranes from unmodified PS and PES are utilized in both flat sheet and hollow fibre forms in ultrafiltration and microfiltration. They are also widely used as porous support in thin film composite membranes for RO desalination.

The commercial aromatic polycarbonates (PC) are a class of polyesters derived from carbonic acid and bisphenol-A. Thin dense films of high molecular weight PC are the most common substrate for the preparation of microporous radiation track membranes. Sulfonated polycarbonates are found¹⁷ to be promising candidates for preparing nanofiltration membranes. Various polymer candidates, generally used in different membrane processes are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Polymers used as membranes in different processes*

Process	Membrane material
MF	Regenerated cellulose, cellulose acetate, polysulfone, polycarbonate, polypropylene, polytetra fluoroethylene, polyvinylidene difluoride, polyamide and polyvinyl chloride
UF	Regenerated cellulose, cellulose acetate, aromatic polyamide, polyamide, polyvinylidene difluoride, polyacrylonitrile
NF	Modified polyamide, polysulfone, cellulose acetate blend
RO	Cellulose acetate, cellulose triacetate, aromatic polyamide, cellulose acetate blend

*Explanation same as in Table 1.

Membrane preparation :

Membranes suitable for pressure driven processes are prepared by phase inversion process which involves preparation of a single phase homogenous polymer solution (or sol) and drawing the polymer solution in the form of a film over a smooth surface and precipitating in a suit-

able gelling medium to form a three-dimensional polymer network (or gel). The polymer solution may incorporate in addition to polymer a solvent, a nonsolvent or a swelling agent and pore-former. Several modifications of this technique are introduced to fabricate various types of membranes from different kinds of polymers. A novel solvent exchange cum immersion purification technique for preparing polyamide membrane has been successfully developed in our laboratory¹⁸.

The wet or combined evaporation-diffusion technique involves partial evaporation of solvent before immersion in a nonsolvent gelation bath where the residual solvent and the pore-former are leached out and exchanged with the solvent. The result is the water-swollen membrane. Wet process adds another step in the membrane making process, namely, partial solvent evaporation – it permits a greater control over the membrane pore size characteristics. The nature and temperature of the gelling bath, and the thermal annealing of post-fabricated membranes, offer additional control variables. A large number of RO, NF and UF membranes are prepared at BARC by this technique.

The technique of preparation of TFC membrane involves preparation of a microporous polysulfone membrane on a non-oven polyester cloth and depositing a polyamide barrier layer over the surface by *in situ* interfacial polymerization. As compared to asymmetric membranes, interfacially synthesized membranes provide high permeation rates without sacrificing selectivity. BARC has developed the laboratory knowhow for interfacial synthesis of polyamide membranes which are suitable for brackish water desalination. Fig. 1 shows typical section of TFC membranes.

(0.15 μm – ultrathin polyamide barrier layer)

(40 μm – microporous polysulfone base matrix)

(120 μm – reinforcing nonwoven polyester fabric)

Fig. 1. Cross-sectional view of typical TFC membrane.

Membrane characterization :

Membrane characterization is an important area in the development of permselective membranes. Membrane char-

acterization involves physical, morphological, phenomenological evaluation under standard reproducible laboratory conditions. Reverse osmosis membranes are often characterized by performance evaluation as well as by using transport models. Characterization of RO membranes in terms of phenomenological coefficients using irreversible thermodynamics and preferential sorption-capillary flow mechanisms are reported¹⁹⁻²¹ from our laboratory. Electrochemical and electrokinetic characterization of RO membranes offer a more simple and versatile approach towards understanding membrane selectivity²². Nanofiltration membranes are generally characterized in terms of surface charges. Presence of surface negative charges on nanofiltration membrane systems are found²³ to markedly affect the selectivity and these membranes show improved selectivity towards anionic species. Ultrafiltration membranes are generally characterized in terms of pore size characteristics, molecular weight cutoff and morphology using electron microscopy^{24,25}.

Applications of membrane processes in BARC

The membranes developed at BARC have been utilized for a wide range of applications involving solute concentrations from nanomolar to molar range. These include separation of trace radionuclides to sea water desalination.

Radioactive liquid effluent treatment :

Large volumes of radioactive effluents are generated in nuclear laboratories which are contaminated with radioactive nuclides in trace level. Reverse osmosis process has been found suitable²⁶⁻²⁸ for preconcentration of such effluents prior to conventional treatment techniques. Cellulose acetate membranes, in plate module configuration, developed in BARC, are successfully demonstrated to decontaminate as well as to concentrate low level radioactive liquid effluents in a pilot scale experiment. Extensive investigations on the effect of ionizing radiations on polymeric membranes were also carried out at BARC^{29,30}. Cellulose acetate membranes have been found to undergo performance degradation when exposed to ionizing radiations in wet conditions, whereas fully aromatic polyamides have better radiation stability.

Decontamination of uranium bearing effluents :

Nanofiltration process was successfully employed in BARC for decontamination of uranium bearing effluents containing high concentrations of ammonium nitrate^{31,32}. High decontamination factors were achieved with reasonably good permeate output in nanofiltration membrane systems in presence of 4% ammonium nitrate in the effluent. Typical results of this study are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Decontamination of ammonium diuranate stream containing ammonium nitrate

Parameter	Data
Membrane material	Cellulose mixed acetate
Uranium concentration in feed	10 ppm
Concentration of ammonium nitrate in feed	4%
Decontamination factor achieved	23
Volume reduction factor	20
Average flux during concentration cycle	360 lmd
Operating pressure	15 bar

DM water production :

Production of boiler quality water or ultrapure water for semi-conductor and pharmaceutical industries by integrating a reverse osmosis system upstream of demineralizer plant is a significant development^{33,34}. This process has been proven to be economically viable where water salinity is higher than 700 ppm. BARC has set up a RO unit ahead of the DM plant at VECC, Kolkata (India) for production of low conductivity water with substantial savings in regenerent chemical cost because RO treated water can be directly fed to the mixed bed polishing unit of DM plant (without sending the stream through the normal path of cation and anion exchange columns).

Brackish water desalination :

Brackish water desalination plants are used to provide potable water to remote villages, affected by salinity of underground water resources. BARC has participated in Technology Mission, constituted by Government of India and set up brackish water desalination plants in remote villages situated in Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat and Rajasthan (India). A typical performance data of a brackish water desalination plant set up at village Sheelgun in Rajasthan is given in Table 5.

Table 5. Salient features of brackish water RO plant at Sheelgun, Rajasthan

Parameter	Data
Feed temperature	31°
Feed concentration	6500 ppm
Operating pressure	20 bar
Product recovery	50%
Permeate rate	1.25 m ³ /h
Pretreatment	Sand filter/cartridge filter/acid and SHMP dosing
Number of RO elements	6 × 4040 spiral wound membrane elements
Product ppm	< 300 ppm

Effluent water treatment :

In developing countries about 90% of the waste water is discharged to water streams without receiving any treatment. In the absence of proper treatment, industrial effluent discharge leads to addition of harmful chemicals and the discharge of domestic water adds to BOD, COD and microorganism content of water bodies affecting the environment. The membrane technology appears to have highly promising role in the treatment of industrial waste water for re-use to address to the growing concern for environment and suggestion for 'zero discharge' of liquid waste into water streams in the coming years. It is always cheaper to adopt waste water treatment through membrane technology for water re-use as compared to augmentation of fresh water through sea water desalination. A 12 m³/h RO plant is being installed at Heavy Water Plant, Tuticorin, to treat the cooling tower blow down stream and recover around 75% of water for re-use. The reject stream from this RO plant is proposed to be utilized for landscaping and gardening. Salient features of this plant are given in Table 6.

Table 6. Salient features of RO plant being setup at HWP, Tuticorin

Parameter	Data
Feed flow	250 lpm
Feed TDS	400 ppm
Permeate flow	200 lpm
Permeate TDS	<10 ppm
Reject flow	50 lpm
Recovery	75%

Concentration of calcium lactobionate stream :

Concentration of calcium lactobionate, a pharmaceutical product of interest for preparation of calcium sandoz, was concentrated from 24 to 48% using nanofiltration systems, in BARC³⁵. This experiment has indicated potential for replacement of thermal evaporation process used presently, resulting in saving of significant amount of energy. Typical results of this study are given in Table 7.

Sea water desalination :

In order to gainfully employ the years of experience and expertise in various aspects of desalination activity on pilot scale, BARC has undertaken³⁶ establishment of a demonstration scale hybrid Multi-Stage Flash-Reverse Osmosis (MSF-RO) desalination plant coupled to our 170 MW(e) PHWR station at Kalpakkam at the South East Coast of India. This desalination project will have a 4500 m³/d (MSF) and 1800 m³/d (RO) to provide 6300 m³/d desalted water

Table 7. Concentration of calcium lactobionate by NF membranes at BARC

Parameter	Data
Membrane material	Cellulose mixed acetate
Performance for 4000 ppm NaCl feed at 22 bar pressure	Flux : 750 lmd SR : 78%
Membrane area	7.2 m ²
Concentration of calcium lactobionate in feed	24%
Concentration of lactose in feed	1.4%
Concentration of NaBr in feed	0.72%
Concentration of lactobionate in concentrate	48%
Average flux	30 lmd
Permeate concentration of calcium lactobionate	1000 ppm
Permeate concentration of NaBr	5000 ppm
Permeate concentration of lactose	180 ppm

which would be enough to meet the dual needs of about 1000 m³/d process water for nuclear power station and drinking water for the neighbouring people. The flow sheet of the plant is shown in Fig. 2. The RO section of this plant is recently commissioned.

BARC has also installed a 100 m³/d seawater desalination plant at Trombay (India) which operates at 50 kg/cm² pressure producing the permeate at 350 ppm TDS in single stage. This facility is also utilized for performance evaluation of spiral modules of RO membranes developed at BARC. The typical performance data of this plant is given in Table 8.

Table 8. Typical performance data of 100 m³/d SWRO Plant, Trombay

Parameter	Data
Average feed TDS	33000 ppm
Operating pressure	52 bar
Permeate TDS	490 ppm
Permeate flux	400 lmd
Solute separation	98.5%
Feed temperature	30°
Recovery	36.3%

UF disinfection and safe water supply :

For economic development of countries like India, the demand for domestic as well as industrial water is rising continuously. Besides providing fresh water through RO technology, pressure-driven membrane processes like UF and MF membrane processes have an important role to play in providing safe drinking water from surface water. The UF plants do not require alum dosing and chlorination and effectively remove turbidity, colour and microorganism.

Fig. 2. 6300 m³/d MSF-RO desalination plant coupled to 170 MWe PHWR : (1) PHWR 170 MWe, (2) HP turbine, (3) moisture separator/reheater, (4) LP turbine, (5) power plant condenser, (6) moderator-DM water cooling loop, (7) DM water-sea water cooling loop, (8) generator, (9) MSF plant chemical pretreatment section, (10) MSF plant brine heater, (11) MSF plant heat recovery section, (12) MSF plant heat reject section, (13) RO plant, (14) RO plant energy recovery turbine, (15) intermediate heat exchanger, (16) product storage tank.

Concluding remarks

In this article, attempts have been made to highlight some of the important development work on membrane based technologies in BARC. There is an urgent need to induct membrane technologies in India to ensure sustainable growth in our growing economy.

The heart of the membrane technology is the membrane itself and for the success of membrane technology, the basic material science of the membrane materials and their interaction with specific industrial problems have to be clearly understood and cleverly exploited to realize the possible improvements in selectivity and membrane life in a cost effective manner.

The service life of membrane material is crucial for integration of its technology in various industrial applications. In fact, the development of appropriate membrane systems for chemical separation in extreme environment of pH, temperature and oxidizing condition is still a challenging task to the scientists and engineers. The availability of technology for manufacture of basic membrane modules on commercial scale is almost non-existent in our country. The membranes available in the international market are monopolized by a few companies. This is a serious drawback which calls for concerted indigenous development work through wider dissemination of knowledge and expertise available at various research centres in the country on a priority basis so that the membrane technologies are inducted at

large scale in various applications in chemical industries in order to ensure the much needed growth in our developing economy without impairing the balance in the life supporting system, viz. water, energy and environment.

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